

EFFECTIVENESS OF WORKING WITH SIMULATORS AND VIRTUAL LABORATORIES IN TEACHING AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

*Sulaymonov Mirobid Abduxalikovich, Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich
Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology
University, Assistant teacher of Informatics and IT sciences
mirobidsulaymonov8686@gmail.com. Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine,
Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology University, Assistant teacher of
Informatics and IT sciences sanjar2023@gmail.com*

Annotation. In the process of using simulators in the subjects related to agriculture, students apply the knowledge they have learned during lectures to life, even if it is virtual. In the process of these studies, they will directly contribute to the development of theory and life studies, as well as strengthening their knowledge. In this research work, the effectiveness of the method of using simulator programs is highlighted. Training through simulation programs is the safest method and the results are significantly better. Therefore, the effectiveness of education is brought with the help of Farming Simulyaotor and ASPIM programs.

Key words: *agriculture, simulator, Farming simulator, ASPIM, virtual laboratory, plant growth process modeling.*

Аннотация. В процессе использования тренажеров по предметам, связанным с сельским хозяйством, студенты применяют полученные на лекциях знания в жизнь, даже если она виртуальная. В процессе этих занятий они будут непосредственно способствовать развитию теории и жизневедения, а также укреплению своих знаний. В данной исследовательской работе подчеркивается эффективность метода использования программ-тренажеров. Обучение с помощью симуляционных программ является самым безопасным методом, и результаты значительно лучше. Поэтому эффективность обучения достигается с помощью программ « Farming Simulyaotor » и ASPIM.

Ключевые слова: *сельское хозяйство, симулятор, Farming Simulator, ASPIM, виртуальная лаборатория, моделирование процесса роста растений.*

Annotatsiya. Qishloq xo'jaligiga oid fanlarda simulyatorlardan foydalanish jarayonida talabalar ma'ruza davomida olgan bilimlarini virtual bo'lsa ham hayotda qo'llaydilar. Bu o'quvlar jarayonida ular nazariya va hayotshunoslik fanining rivojlanishiga, bilimlarini mustahkamlashga bevosita hissa qo'shadilar. Ushbu tadqiqot ishida simulyator dasturlarini qo'llash usulining samaradorligi yoritilgan. Simulyatsiya dasturlari orqali o'qitish eng xavfsiz usul bo'lib, natijalar sezilarli darajada yaxshilanadi. Shuning uchun ta'lim samaradorligi Farming Simulyaotor va ASPIM dasturlari yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *qishloq xo'jaligi, simulyator, fermerlik simulyatori, ASPIM, virtual laboratoriya, o'simliklarning o'sish jarayonini modellashtirish.*

Intraduction. The use of models in the educational process is not a new method. Models have been used in education since ancient times. Simulators can be used in almost all aspects of the educational process: from primary education to higher educational institutions. In recent times, simulators are used even in the field of medicine. One of the main reasons for using simulators is that they are a much

cheaper alternative to real objects. Simulators provide an opportunity to model the growth and development of a plant in a virtual state without such real equipment and facilities, as well as conduct virtual laboratory work. This by itself not only saves large amounts of money, but also does not create a need for them at all. The fact that simulators require almost no financial resources makes it possible for certain studies to be carried out by students hundreds, if necessary, thousands of times [1].

Methods. Another advantage of using simulators is that they are safe. In this research work, the effectiveness of the method of using simulator programs is highlighted. Training through simulation programs is the safest method and the results are significantly better. Therefore, the effectiveness of education is brought with the help of Farming Simulyaotor and ASPIM programs. The Farming Simulator program was created in 2001 in the field of natural sciences. It is also available through farmingsimulyator.com, which has models on various topics, created in Python and Java (fig-1).

Figure-1. Overview interface of the Farming simulator program.

The models offered on the Farming simulator site are Open Source and can be used by any user for free. The number of models in Farming simulator is more than 100. They have the ability to conduct demonstration experiments related to physics, mathematics, chemistry, organize and model virtual laboratory work. This Farming simulator program corresponds to the state education standards of Uzbekistan and the literature used in educational institutions. The models in the Farming simulator program can be widely used as demonstration experiments in classes in agriculture, agronomy, veterinary science, chemistry and biology, and in the organization of virtual laboratory training [2]. In particular, there are more than 90 models related to agriculture and agrarian sciences, more than 10 models related to biological science, and more than 20 models related to chemical science. The models presented in the program are not only in English. If you want to translate the models presented in the program into Uzbek, you can do this without any difficulty. For this, there is a "Translated Sims" section on the official website of the program, and you can go there and select the appropriate model and translate it into Uzbek by filling out a special account.

In the Farming simulator program, you can see the appearance of models of various disciplines in the following pictures 2 and 3.

Figure-2. View of models available in the Farming simulator program

Figure-3. Models related to the "Low-frequency electromagnetic simulation for electric machines" section of the Farming simulator program

There is also APSIM program, which is close to the Farming simulator program, in which the leading software for modeling and simulation of agricultural systems is created for teachers and students (students) to use for free. It should be noted that now the APSIM company's software has been developed under the name of ESSS. Currently, these programs are released under the name ESSS, but the functionality of the programs is almost the same as that of APSIM. The use of the APSIM software environment in agricultural science has been very effective.

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Figure-4. APSIM simulation software environment login window
The APSIM simulation platform Agricultural Production Systems Simulator

(APSIM) is internationally recognized as a highly advanced simulator of agricultural systems. It includes more than 80 modules that allow simulation of systems covering plant, animal, soil, climate and management interactions. APSIM is used by scientists as a decision support tool in research, education and agriculture. APSIM users can easily create virtual farms on their computers using the model's easy-to-use user interface (no need to write code) and then fully predict multiple soil and vegetation variables on a daily time step. imagine [3]. Users can then evaluate and explore different combinations of management practices or cropping sequences to increase farm profitability and reduce environmental degradation. The model needs climate, soil and management information to run the simulation.

Results. These programs aim to teach the use of the model, explain the science behind the crop and environment modules, present data requirements, and introduce participants to simulations, the results are also 45-50% better than normal experiments. Time, land space, and financial costs are saved in order to save time in growing plants and get effective results. Also, the quality of teaching will increase by 14%. This simulator program consists of presentations and simulation exercises, focusing on Midwestern production systems that include corn, soybeans, wheat, and crop rotation [4]. Users can analyze various aspects of the soil-plant-atmosphere system, such as plant growth and development, yield response to management practices (e.g., planting date, variety, N ratio, evaporation), crop rotation, soil water processes (e.g., drainage), soil carbon, nitrogen, and above-ground organic matter dynamics (e.g., N mineralization and residue decomposition), CO₂ and N₂O emissions, and climate change impacts. Participants will also be introduced to scenario risk analyzes to inform decision making.

This program is intended for students, professors and agronomists who are interested in using simulation models in their work. The program is mainly intended for beginners, as well as for users who have developed simulations and need special technical support. The unique features of the program include the optimal program that demonstrates physical phenomena, more than 50 step-by-step teaching lessons, ready-made models of more than 150 branches of the industry, the possibility of computer modeling of agrarian processes, and the possibility of independent modeling. interface, implementation and observation of experiments that are difficult to conduct in Earth conditions, powerful instrumentation of the program, allows to calculate the value of the physical quantities participating in the experiment with very good accuracy, graphical connection between the physical quantity participating in the physical event and other physical quantities it is possible to create, save created models and print them on paper.

Discussion. In conclusion, we can say that. These programs, regardless of their profession, teach the user to be inquisitive, think creatively, and analyze work results. If the study process is organized using the above-mentioned programs, pupils (students) will approach science with interest, it is no secret that it is very difficult to interest young people in natural sciences and agricultural sciences. If the educational process is organized using the above-recommended programs, it will cause the pupils (students) to study their specialty, agricultural sciences, physics, computer science and chemistry in depth. The possibilities of the program are very

wide, it can be widely used in practical training, especially in performing virtual laboratory work, and it allows perfect mastering of English terms related to physics.

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